

A Novel Attention-guided 3D-CNN Framework for Alzheimer's Disease Classification

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Abstract

Alzheimer's disease is a devastating illness that frequently leads to dementia and is a major cause of death among the elderly, posing a significant global health challenge. The alarming statistic that one in three elderly individuals will develop dementia or Alzheimer's underscores the growing urgency of this problem. This study presents a novel 3D-CNN model enhanced with an attention mechanism for more accurate detection and classification of Alzheimer's disease from MRI scans. The model combines the power of CNNs and MLPs to improve both feature extraction and classification performance. To automatically identify and prioritize crucial features in Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) scans, this study employed spatial attention mechanisms, eliminating the need for manual feature selection. Evaluated on the ADNI dataset, the model achieved cutting-edge classification accuracies of 97.86% (Alzheimer's disease (AD) vs. Normal Control (NC)), 90.65% (Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) vs. Normal Control (NC)), and 92.18% (Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) vs. Alzheimer's disease (AD)), surpassing previous approaches.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease (AD), 3D-Convolutional Neural Network (3D-CNN), Attention mechanism, Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), Feature extraction.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) poses a significant global health threat, with a new case diagnosed at a startling rate of roughly every three seconds (Adaobi *et al.*, 2023). It stands as a primary cause of dementia and mortality among older adults globally (Khan *et al.*, 2023). Though clinically well-characterized, its underlying cause remains unclear (Nichols *et al.*, 2022). AD's progressive neurodegeneration, marked by amyloid plaques and tau tangles, results in structural and functional brain changes (Hempel *et al.*, 2021). Its symptoms, including memory loss and cognitive decline, worsen over time, severely affecting daily life (Zhao *et al.*, 2023). Prompt diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease (AD) and its precursor,

Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), is critical for optimal treatment and management (Livingston *et al.*, 2020). Computer-aided diagnosis, utilizing neuroimaging, is emerging as a valuable alternative to traditional methods that are largely dependent on clinical expertise (Zhao *et al.*, 2023).

For managing Alzheimer's disease (AD), neuroimaging techniques like MRI and Positron Emission Tomography (PET) are crucial for diagnosis and tracking disease progression (Shoeibi *et al.*, 2023). These techniques allow for the visualization of structural and functional alterations in the brain, including atrophy and the buildup of abnormal proteins (Zhou *et al.*, 2023).

Machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) approaches, utilizing large datasets of medical images for automatic feature extraction, have emerged as valuable tools for early AD detection (Frimpong *et al.*, 2023). Due to their capability to learn hierarchical representations directly from data, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have become a popular tool in medical image analysis (Tang *et al.*, 2024). In particular, three-dimensional CNNs (3D-CNNs) demonstrate superior performance in capturing spatial and temporal relationships within volumetric data, rendering them highly suitable for the analysis of brain MRI and PET scans (George *et al.*, 2023). These models have demonstrated superior generalizability and robustness to image quality variations, crucial for clinical applications (George *et al.*, 2023).

Attention mechanisms, drawing inspiration from human selective attention, have become integral to DL architectures, enhancing model performance and interpretability (Niu *et al.*, 2021). By focusing on salient details, they improve the extraction of informative features from medical images (Hassanin *et al.*, 2024). In AD research, attention mechanisms can highlight relevant regions in brain scans, assisting in disease classification and prediction (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). Ultimately, improving the accuracy of AD detection is paramount due to the intricacies of design and detection characteristics. This work, therefore, aimed to review effective AD detection by incorporating attention mechanisms and 3D-CNNs into AD applications. The integration of attention mechanisms into 3D-CNNs seeks to enhance detection speed and accuracy. Although 3D-CNNs and attention mechanisms are distinct techniques used in AD detection, this research hybridized them to improve

accuracy. This approach differs from numerous schemes relying solely on a single technique for AD detection. The overall design constitutes an improved AD detection system using attention mechanisms and 3D-CNNs. The proposed work will also make several unique contributions to previously developed AD detection systems.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Alzheimer's disease has been a major global health concern, with a high rate of new diagnoses (Adaobi *et al.*, 2023). Although its root cause is unknown (Nichols *et al.*, 2022), machine learning techniques, including 3D-Convolutional Neural Network, CNNs and Multilayer Perceptron, MLPs, have shown promise in AD prediction using neuroimaging data (Hassanin *et al.*, 2024; Frimpong *et al.*, 2023). While existing models are effective, there's room for improvement in terms of computational efficiency and convergence. This research aims to enhance AD detection using 3D-CNNs and attention mechanisms, with a focus on optimizing model parameters and reducing training time.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

This study is aimed at developing a 3D-CNN architecture using Attention Mechanism for detecting of Alzheimer's disease. The specific objectives include to: formulate architectural design framework for an improved 3D-CNN and attention mechanism with Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) as the classifier; developed a 3D-CNN and attention mechanism model with multilayer perceptron (MLP) for detecting and classifying Alzheimer's disease; implement the proposed developed model in python environment; and evaluate the model performance using standard metrics such as sensitivity, specificity and accuracy.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Table 1: Comparison among Papers with 3D-CNN- Attention Model

S/N	Author	Method	Modalities	Data	Accuracy (%)	Limitation(s)
1.	Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2020	1D-CNN and Self-Attention Mechanisms This study developed three explainable deep learning models for Alzheimer's detection using language features, specifically part-of-speech and embeddings. Incorporating self-attention and a 1D CNN, the models generate intra-class and inter-class explanations.	MRI	Dementia-Bank	92.20	1D-CNN has a limited access to the region of interest and hence limiting the accuracy of the study's model.
2.	Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2021	DC-CNN, 3D-CNN and Connection-wise Attention Mechanisms. This paper presented a novel densely connected CNN featuring connection-wise attention for classifying Alzheimer's disease using brain MRI scans.	MRI	ADNI	91.3	Training remained computationally expensive, even though the input data size was reduced by utilizing MR patches rather than entire brain images. Even after adjusting parameters like the number of layers and the size and number of kernels during training, the deep CNN model still struggled to achieve network convergence.
3.	Nithya <i>et al.</i> , 2023	3D-CNN. This study introduced a novel 3D-CNN architecture for predicting AD using MRI data, surpassing existing approaches in accuracy. This model, validated with ADNI data, outperformed LSTM-RNN, SAE-DNN, D-CNN, 2D-CNN, Inception-V4, and ResNet, offering enhanced intelligent diagnosis and reduced human effort.	MRI	ADNI	89.27	The proposed 3D-CNN model should be evaluated on various other AD datasets and for diagnosing other brain-related diseases to assess its generalizability and effectiveness across different scenarios.
4.	Sudheesh <i>et al.</i> , 2023	2D, 3D-CNN and Transfer Learning. This study explored the use of transfer learning methods based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for predicting Alzheimer's disease from MRI scans. Utilizing ADNI data, the study employed 2D and 3D-CNN architectures to interpret brain images.	MRI	ADNI	93.24	Pre-trained convolutional layers, such as those from AlexNet, which are capable of extracting generic image features, could serve as effective input features.

Table 1(contd.): Comparison among Papers with 3D-CNN- Attention Model

S/N	Author	Method	Modalities	Data	Accuracy (%)	Limitation(s)
5.	George <i>et al.</i> , 2023	3D-CNN with Attention Mechanism This paper introduced a novel 3D-CNN architecture with attention mechanisms for AD detection using whole-brain MRI images. Leveraging channel and spatial attention mechanisms, the model accurately identified brain dysfunctions by focusing on specific brain regions.	MRI	ADNI	79.0%	The low complexity of the proposed pipeline is confirmed by the simplicity of the CNN framework, which consists of just five convolutional layers.
6.	Frimpong <i>et al.</i> , 2023	3D-CNN-MLP with Attention Mechanism A 3D-CNN-MLP model incorporating an Attention Mechanism for relevant feature extraction from MRI scans was introduced in this study for Alzheimer's disease classification.	MRI	ADNI	91.27%	The proposed method was computationally expensive for training due to the patch size and has not fully resolved convergence issues when altering the parameters.
7.	Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2024	MOSEGCN and GCN This research introduced MOSEGCN, a novel method for integrating diverse biological data. MOSEGCN uniquely integrates Transformer models, employing multi-head self-attention, with Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs).	MRI	ADNI	83.0%	While MOSEGCN effectively integrates various biological data types for disease diagnosis, it is currently limited to only three specific data types. Whether MOSEGCN can process more than three data types, particularly diverse sources like imaging data, remains untested and warrants further investigation.
8.	Ning <i>et al.</i> , 2024	3D-CNN and ADAS-Cog13 This study trained 3D CNN models to predict ADAS-Cog13 sub-scores using MRI and FDG-PET data. Analysis revealed distinct brain feature associations for cognitive sub-scores in each modality, highlighting the importance of exploring multiple imaging modalities for understanding AD etiology.	MRI and PET	ADNI	88.9%	The limitations of this study include first, to increase the sample size, the study combined MCI and CN participants into a single nAD class, which may have obscured differences between MCI and CN brain characteristics. Secondly, the reliance on existing knowledge for the 3D-CNN model's structure and parameters presents an opportunity to improve accuracy by exploring more

Table 1(contd.): Comparison among Papers with 3D-CNN- Attention Model

S/N	Author	Method	Modalities	Data	Accuracy (%)	Limitation(s)
						combinations. Third, the study defined brain feature importance using the occlusion method, but alternative methods like GRAD-RAM could offer additional insights. Finally, the model only predicts cognitive function at a single point in time; a logical next step would be to incorporate a temporal dimension to forecast future cognitive changes.
9.	Rogeu <i>et al.</i> , 2024	3D-CNN and VGG16 This research introduced and validated a 3D neural network for classifying AD, FTD, or CN subjects based on brain glucose metabolism using [18F]-FDG-PET scans.	PET	ADFLI	89.9%	Limitations include firstly, subjects from the same center could not be provided for all three categories, potentially leading to acquisition-specific biases. For example, the CN category lacked ULille subjects because the study clinical database does not include healthy controls. This situation underscores a general challenge for AI development in clinical settings: the scarcity of healthy controls among hospital patients. Furthermore, although data augmentation can theoretically introduce bias between classes, it was crucial for expanding the training dataset. The lack of underfitting, however, suggests that any bias introduced was likely minimal.
10	Hassan and Wagler, 2024	CNN and GAT This study proposed a segmentation method for biomedical images using CNNs and graph attention networks (GATs).	MRI	ADNI	86.5%	Despite the success of GATs in various tasks, stemming from their attention mechanisms' ability to capture node interactions, a potential drawback is their limited generalizability to graphs with unfamiliar structures compared to standard graph convolutional operations. And for complex tasks like AD cell type image segmentation, its performance may be limited.

3.0 METHODS

3.1 Proposed Model

This study is aim at creating a robust deep-learning model for the classification of Alzheimer's disease (AD). The architecture, built upon a 3D-CNN-MLP framework, will process raw MRI data to identify the region of interest (ROI). Following this, a 3D-CNN will be used to extract distinctive features from the ROI. These feature maps will then be used to generate a probability map,

highlighting the likelihood of features surpassing or falling below a defined threshold. Finally, this probability map will be input into the MLP for classification and prediction of AD. This proposed approach integrates a deep residual block of convolution to emphasize key features. Moreover, to address variations at the cell scale, we will incorporate a spatial attention mechanism to enhance feature information and improve prediction accuracy.

Figure 1. Proposed Architectural Design Framework

3.2 Required Phases

3.2.1 Dataset Acquisition and Pre-processing

Public datasets like Alzheimer’s disease Neuroimaging Initiatives (ADNI), containing neuroimaging, genetic, and clinical data, have significantly advanced artificial intelligence research in Alzheimer's disease, aiding in the development of diagnostic tools. This study used the ADNI database, which includes 3,100 participants with T1 and T2 weighted MRI scans. The scans was preprocessed and standardized for analysis. Preprocessing is essential for making MRI data suitable for deep learning classification.

It involves techniques like registration, normalization, and noise removal to enhance contrast and manage pixel intensity. In this study, raw MRI scans was preprocessed using a standard pipeline, including linear image registration, skull-stripping, segmentation, intensity normalization, and outlier clipping. Histogram normalization, also known as histogram stretching or contrast stretching, enhanced image contrast by redistributing pixel values to utilize the full intensity range. It involves computing the histogram of the original image, identifying its minimum and maximum intensity values, and applying a

linear transformation to each pixel. This transformation maps the original intensity values to a desired range, usually the full range available.

$$\text{new}_{\text{pixel_value}} = \frac{\text{pixel_value} - \text{original_min}}{\text{original_max} - \text{original_min}} \times \text{NewMax} - \text{NewMin} + \text{NewMin} \dots\dots\dots(i)$$

Where: pixel_value is the original intensity value of the pixel, original_min and original_max are the minimum and maximum intensity values in the original image, NewMin and NewMax are the desired minimum and maximum intensity values in the normalized image.

After normalization, voxel intensities was clipped to the [-1, 2.5] range. Background voxels was removed, and key brain regions like the Entorhinal Area and Hippocampus was used for classification. All data was standardized to have zero mean and unit variance.

$$A_n(i, j) = \frac{a(i, j) - \text{mean}(a_j)}{\text{std}(a_j)} \dots\dots\dots(ii)$$

Where the jth column of the matrix (A) is denoted as $A_{i,j}$

3.2.2 Feature Extraction by 3D-CNN Enhanced with Attention Mechanism

For Alzheimer's disease detection, this study extracted features from 3D MRI data using a 3D-CNN modeled after the DenseNet121 architecture. It improves upon traditional methods by leveraging spatial relationships and incorporating an attention mechanism. The attention mechanism focuses on the most relevant features, allowing the model to make more accurate predictions. Unlike DenseNet, which combines features from all previous layers, this model selectively integrates features using a probability map algorithm. The model also incorporates the ResNet connection method and utilizes feature maps from all previous layers, further improving its efficiency and accuracy.

3.3 Classification

The Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) is the machine learning algorithm that can be used for classification. It works by recognizing patterns in data and predicting each pixel's class membership. In this study, features from a 3D-Attention probability map were fed into an MLP for AD classification. The MLP was trained using the cross-entropy loss function, known for its effectiveness in similar scenarios.

The loss function L is represented in (iii) as:

$$L = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log(\tilde{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \tilde{y}_i)] \dots\dots\dots(iii)$$

Where N is the samples number, then, y_i is the true label, and \tilde{y}_i is the probability predicted for the positive class.

3.4 Evaluation of Performance Metrics

The evaluation of all models was done using metrics such as accuracy, specificity, and sensitivity with the formula in (iv), (v) and (vi) respectively.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TN+TP}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \dots\dots\dots(iv)$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \dots\dots\dots(v)$$

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \dots\dots\dots(vi)$$

Where: TN = True Negative, TP = True Positive, FP = False Positive and FN = False Negative

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Datasets

The research data used for this study came from the ADNI database, a public resource for Alzheimer's research. 3,100 participants with specific brain scans were included. They were divided into three groups: healthy individuals, Alzheimer's patients, and those with mild cognitive impairment. Table 2 shows more details about the participants.

Table 2: Information about the Participants and Data in the Study

		NC	MCI	AD
Gender	Female	819	721	600
	Male	435	310	215
Age		66.4 ± 5.0	71.3 ± 5.6	77.1 ± 8.2
Clinical Dementia Rating (CDR)		0 ± 0	1.5 ± 0.2	1.2 ± 0.5
Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE)		29.10 ± 1.0	27.40 ± 1.70	19.09 ± 5.55

To standardize brain scans, the MRI images were resized to 224 x 224 x 224. The dataset included 3,100 records, divided into AD, MCI, and NC categories. Data augmentation was used to increase the training set to 9,273 images. The classification system was built using Pytorch and trained for 100 epochs. The model was tested on three tasks: AD versus NC, MCI versus NC, and MCI versus AD.

4.2 Results Presentation, Evaluation, and Comparison with Other CNNs

The model in this study achieved high classification accuracy for AD versus NC (97.86%), MCI versus NC (90.65%), and MCI versus AD (92.18%), outperforming models like VGG16 and DenseNet. It also showed good sensitivity and specificity. The basic CNN model had lower accuracy in distinguishing AD from healthy controls.

Table 3: Presentation of the Result of Extraction and Classification Activities of this Study

Classification	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Testing Time	Training Time
AD versus NC	97.86%	91.46%	98.98%		
MCI versus NC	90.65%	85.75%	88.18%	1.10 sec.	1.14 sec.
MCI versus AD	92.18%	88.98%	90.98%		

DenseNet improved accuracy for AD versus NC classification to 88.90%. Further modifications with self-attention increased accuracy to 91.27% for AD vs. MCI. Nevertheless, the model developed in this study demonstrated superior overall performance, achieving the highest accuracy rates across all tasks. For MCI vs. NC, accuracies ranged between 71% and 76%,

with this study's method again showing the highest accuracy. Compared to other models, this model also had the highest average performance and lowest computation time. Detailed results can be found in Table 4. Furthermore, in Table 5 and 6 the comparison of the average performance and computation time of this study's model against other existing models is presented.

Table 4: Comparison of this Study's Classification Results to other Top Methods

Methods		Zhao et al., 2020	Bi et al., 2020	Zhang et al., 2021	Frimpong et al., 2023	This Study
AD vs. NC	ACC	82.78	87.89	91.30	91.27	97.86
	SEN	83.09	84.50	87.32	88.73	91.46
	SPE	82.50	91.25	90.00	93.75	98.98
MCI vs. NC	ACC	70.49	76.10	82.12	80.85	90.65
	SEN	70.66	76.00	74.66	77.33	85.75
	SPE	70.00	76.25	75.00	86.25	88.18
MCI vs. AD	ACC	74.44	81.83	82.45	87.34	92.18
	SEN	73.23	80.28	81.69	84.50	88.98
	SPE	76.00	86.11	82.66	81.33	90.98

Table 5: Comparison of this Study Model's Average Results to other Top Methods for Classifying Alzheimer's Disease

Authors	Dataset	Average Performance
Zhao <i>et al.</i> , 2020	ADNI	77.39%
Bi <i>et al.</i> , 2020	ADNI	83.27%
Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2021	ADNI	84.82%
Frimpong <i>et al.</i> , 2023	ADNI	91.27%
This Study's Model	ADNI	97.86%

Table 6: Comparison of this Study Model's Computation Time to other Top Methods

Authors	Testing Time	Training Time
Zhao <i>et al.</i> , 2020	2.31 sec.	2.39 sec.
Bi <i>et al.</i> , 2020	2.00 sec.	2.26 sec.
Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2021	1.44 sec.	1.48 sec.
Frimpong <i>et al.</i> , 2023	1.28 sec.	1.31sec
This Study's Model	1.10 sec.	1.14 sec.

This study investigated early Alzheimer's detection via brain MRI scans. A new method employing a 3D-CNN with an attention mechanism was developed by researchers to improve the process of feature extraction. While deeper CNNs like DenseNet have shown improvements, this study's model further enhances accuracy and efficiency by selectively prioritizing important features. Results indicate superior performance compared to basic CNN and DenseNet models.

5.0 CONCLUSION

A novel model for predicting Alzheimer's disease was developed in this study using MRI data from 3,100 participants. The model, combining 3D-CNN and an attention mechanism, achieved high classification accuracies, outperforming traditional methods. This approach enables automatic identification of crucial features in MRI scans, aiding in distinguishing between Alzheimer's disease, Mild Cognitive Impairment, and Normal Control.

6.0 CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE AND FUTURE WORK

This study contributes significantly to deep learning-based Alzheimer's disease

detection by developing a novel and robust 3D-CNN model with an integrated attention mechanism, leading to improved classification accuracy. The model achieves top-ranked accuracy, eliminating the need for manual feature selection. It also contributes to the development of automated tools for early AD diagnosis, and provides insights for further research in this area. Future research could focus on improving convergence, reducing computational cost, and utilizing more diverse datasets beyond ADNI for Alzheimer's disease detection.

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to publish and preparation of the manuscript.

9.0 CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

10.0 AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS

Nurudeen Olawale Ibrahim: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing-Original Draft.

Kamil Kayode Saka: Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Validation.

Aliu Adebayo Seriki: Investigation, Resources, Visualization.

Morufat Damola Gbolagade: Supervision, Project Administration, Writing-Review & Editing.

All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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